

SOCIAL RECOGNITION, MANAGERIAL SUPPORT AND WORKERS' AFFECTIVE JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the influence of social recognition, managerial support on workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State, Nigeria. Descriptive research design of the survey type was adopted for the study. The sample for the study consisted of 798 teaching and non-teaching staff from three (3) public universities in Ondo State through multi-stage sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was tagged social recognition and managerial support Questionnaire (SRMSQ) with reliability index of = 0.72. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics. The research questions were answered with frequency distributions, percentages and mean. The decision level was based on weighted mean score of 2.5. Findings revealed that the extent of social recognition for workers was low ($\bar{X}=2.0$) and managerial support for workers in public universities was high ($\bar{X}=2.9$). The results also revealed that social recognition via awards of excellence, words of commendation and managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities. Based on these findings, it was recommended that school management and Head of Departments should endeavour to give members staff the needed support for career growth and annual award excellence to recognise outstanding workers.

Keywords: Social Recognition, Managerial Support, Affective commitment, Workers, Universities

Introduction

Since workers are essential to achieving the goals of tertiary institutions, school administrators are expected to encourage practices that will strengthen their affective job commitment. These workers-friendly practices include social recognition and managerial support. In an organisation, social recognition signals to members of staff that their efforts, achievements, contributions and knowledge are valued by their superiors and management (Ahmad, Bibi, Bilal & Hussain, 2020). Recognising workers' contributions and efforts towards organisational success can be delivered through formal and informal processes. The formal structure is the officially approved social recognition programmes designed to reward outstanding workers in public tertiary institutions such as monthly or annual awards of excellence, letters of commendation from management, presentation of customised plaques, and publishing the names of outstanding worker(s) on institution website. This type of social recognition has set standards and criteria for selecting benefitting workers.

The informal social recognition of workers refers to as unstructured means of recognising workers' efforts towards organisational success. Informal social recognition for workers includes unscheduled events or daily appreciation of an individual or group of workers for their feat such as words of commendation from superiors or colleagues, refreshments, and gift cards among others. Series of research works indicate that non-financial rewards such as recognition and other intrinsic rewards are sine qua non for affective dimension of job commitment. Burmansah, Sujanto and Mukhtar (2019), assert that if social recognition is properly carry out, it can increase commitment and enthusiasm of workers. Furthermore, Currivan (2000) and Degago (2014), submit that recognition can motivate, helping to build feelings of confidence, satisfaction, inspire loyalty as well as encouraging workers to extend their efforts.

Managerial support refers to the interpersonal association between the manager and worker within an organisation. Basically, head of departments, managers or directors are the link

between senior management and members of staff in an organisation. Hence, workers who receive support from their superiors may positively influence their passion (affection) for their job. This support can manifest in diverse ways such as management involving members of staff in decisions making processes, effective communication channels to offer solutions to workers agitations and management professional guidance to assist workers in carrying out their work effectively among others. Many studies have shown that managerial support is one of the most significant factors for job commitment (Danesi, 2011; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Allen, & Helms, 2002). Corroborating this, Fu & Deshpande (2013), argue that workers who receive more support from their superiors show more commitment to their organisation than those who receives less support. According to Zeinabadi and Salehi (2011), a worker would have a good attitude towards their organisation when their superiors provide ample support in return. Moruri, Evans and Jennifer (2018) submit that that if managers shows serious concern for the advancement of his/her members of staff, the workers would reciprocate in similar way, which will help to maintain a positive working relationship by linking workers to the organisation objectives.

Affective job commitment according to Agyemang and Ofei (2013), is an individual worker's identification with goals and values of an organisation, characterise by an intention to remain in it, willingness to put in extra effort on its behalf and strong desire to maintain membership of the organisation. Ambad and Bahron (2012) submit that those with strong affective commitment continue employment with the organisation because they genuinely want to do so. That is, workers with affective commitment have a strong sense of belonging which increases their involvement in organisational activities. They are more willing to help organisations' pursue their goals. In a study, Tafamel and Akrawah (2019) found that when workers perceive that there are favourable organisational rewards, their affective commitment increases. Esther, Byron, Wilson, Forcheh, Linn and Fako (2019) assessed the affective commitment of academics in a university in Botswana. The findings showed that only 34.1% of academic employees sampled had affective commitment. These and other findings necessitated the needs to study if social recognition and managerial support will influence workers' affective job commitment in public tertiary institutions in Ondo State.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the unique roles of tertiary institutions in providing qualitative education to Nigeria citizens, workers are complaining about a series of challenges, such as unfriendly workers policies by government and school management, lack of support for career growth, unpleasant working environment and lack of social recognition among others in public universities in Ondo State. These problems sometimes dampened the moral of workers which often leads to low affective job commitment such as workers absenteeism, dereliction of duties, indifference attitudes to work, lateness and workers' resignation for better offer elsewhere. It is with this view that the study examined social recognition, managerial support and workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

This study examined social recognition, managerial support and workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study were to:

1. investigate the extent of social recognition for workers public universities in Ondo State;
2. ascertain the extent of managerial support for workers in public universities in Ondo State;
3. examine the influence of social recognition on workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State; and
4. investigate the influence of managerial support on workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of social recognition for workers public universities in Ondo State?
2. What is the extent of managerial support for workers in public universities in Ondo State?
3. Does social recognition for workers' influence affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State?
4. Does managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State?

Methodology

The study adopted s descriptive research design of the survey type. The sample for the study consisted of 798 teaching and non-teaching staff from three (3) public universities namely: Adekunle Ajasin University Akungba-Akoko (278); Federal University of Technology, Akure (421); and Olusegun Agagu University of Science and Technology, Okitipupa (99) located across the three senatorial districts in Ondo State through stratified proportional sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was tagged social recognition and managerial support Questionnaire (SRMSQ) with reliability index of = 0.72. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics. The research questions were answered with frequency distributions, percentages and mean. The decision level was based on weighted mean score of 2.5.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Research Question 1:

What is the extent of social recognition for workers public universities in Ondo State?

Table 1

Extent of Social Recognition in Public Universities in Ondo State

SN	Statement	Always No	%	Some times No	%	Rarely No	%	Not At All No	%	X	Remark	
1	Award of excellence is given to workers by management in recognition of their dedication to duties	127	16%	264	33%	202	25%	206	26%	2.3	Not Accepted	
2	Workers receive words of commendation for their positive contributions towards organisational success	97	12%	477	60%	68	9%	157	20%	2.6	Accepted	
3	Letter of commendation is given to workers as a sign of recognising their efforts	98	12%	156	20%	162	20%	383	48%	1.9	Not Accepted	
4	Names of outstanding workers are published in institution website for recognition	40	5%	93	12%	399	50%	267	33%	1.8	Not Accepted	
5	Institution has open board that contain congratulatory messages to exemplary workers.	39	5%	103	13%	103	13%	554	69%	1.5	Not Accepted	
6	Management presents customised plaques to workers as a tangible reminder of their accomplishments	28	4%	107	13%	340	43%	324	41%	1.8	Not Accepted	
7	Photographs of best performing workers are display in a specific location within institution premises for recognition	79	10%	102	13%	220	28%	398	50%	1.7	Not Accepted	
Average Total		72	9%	186	23%	213	27%	327	41%			
Grand Mean											2.1	

Source: Fieldwork (January (2022))

In Table 1, the mean scores on items 1-7 on social recognition revealed that from various methods used in recognition of workers' outstanding performances in public universities in Ondo

State, words of commendation has the highest mean score ($\bar{X}=2.6$), followed by award of excellence ($\bar{X}=2.3$) and letter of commendation ($\bar{X}=1.9$). Other least methods rarely used to recognise workers' efforts was the use of institution website ($\bar{X}=1.8$), presentation of customised plaques to workers ($\bar{X}=1.8$), displaying photographs of best performing workers in specific location ($\bar{X}=1.7$) and use of open board to display names of outstanding workers ($\bar{X}=1.5$). Also, Table 1 revealed a grand total of 32% of respondents that affirmed the existence of social recognition activities for workers in public universities institutions while 68% expressed contrary view. It equally showed a grand mean of 2.1 which was below decision level of 2.5 weighted mean. Hence, question one was answered that the extent of social recognition for workers in public universities in Ondo State was low.

Research Question 2

What is the extent of managerial support for workers in public universities in Ondo State?

Table 2

Extent of Managerial Support in Public Universities in Ondo State

SN	Statement	Always No	%	Some times No	%	Rarely No	%	Not At All No	%	X	Remark	
8	Management promptly approve workers' request to embark on study leave	233	29%	478	60%	56	7%	32	4%	3.1	Accepted	
9	Institution provides effective communication channels to offer solutions to workers agitations	186	23%	465	58%	111	14%	37	5%	3.0	Accepted	
10	Workers receive moral support from management to embark on career development programmes	212	27%	477	60%	79	10%	31	4%	3.0	Accepted	
11	Workers receive professional guidance from the management to effectively carry out their official duties.	170	21%	403	50%	118	15%	108	14%	2.7	Accepted	
Average Total		200	25%	456	57%	91	12%	52	7%			
Grand Mean											3.0	

Source: Fieldwork (January (2022))

From Table 2, the mean scores on items 8-11 on managerial support revealed that the support received by workers to embark on career development has the highest mean ($\bar{X}=3.1$), followed by management prompt approval of workers' study leave ($\bar{X}=3.0$), effective communication channels to offer solutions to workers agitations ($\bar{X}=3.0$) and professional guidance from management ($\bar{X}=2.7$). A total of 82% of respondents supported the statements on managerial support while those who negated the assertion was 18% and a grand mean score of 3.0 which was above decision level of 2.5 weighted mean. Thus, question two was answered that the extent of managerial support for workers in public universities in Ondo State was high.

Research Question 3

Does social recognition influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State?

Table 3

Social Recognition and Workers' Affective Job Commitment in Public Universities in Ondo State

SN	Statement	SA No	%	A No	%	D No	%	SD No	%	X	Remark	
12	Words of commendation for workers on their inputs towards attainment of organisational goals elicit job commitment	521	65%	253	32%	20	3%	5	1%	3.6	Accepted	
13	Featuring outstanding workers on institution magazine website as a form of recognising their contributions leads to job commitment	600	75%	54	7%	110	14%	35	4%	3.5	Accepted	
14	Honouring best performing workers by displaying their photographs in a specific location within institution premises increases job commitment	331	41%	359	45%	68	9%	41	5%	3.2	Accepted	
15	Recognising workers efforts through award ceremony promotes job commitment	574	72%	214	27%	7	1%	4	1%	3.7	Accepted	
16	Social recognition for workers does not enhance job commitment	9	1%	18	2%	247	31%	525	66%	1.3	Accepted	
Average Total		407	51%	179.6	23%	90.4	12%	122	15%			
Grand Mean											3.0	

Source: Fieldwork (January (2022))

Table 3 showed mean scores ranging from 1.3 to 3.6 of items 12-16 on influence of social recognition on affective job commitment in public universities. It also showed that 74% of total respondents were in support of the items while 26% were not in support. It equally showed a grand mean score of 3.0 which was above the decision level of 2.5 weighted mean. Therefore, question three was answered that social recognition influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State.

Research Question 4

Does managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State?

Table 4

Managerial Support and Workers' Affective Job Commitment in Public Universities in Ondo State

SN	Statement	SA No	%	A No	%	D No	%	SD No	%	X	Remark	
17	Job commitment increases through involvement of members of staff in decision making processes	300	38%	382	48%	72	9%	45	6%	3.1	Accepted	
18	Opportunity given to workers to discuss their challenges with management raises their job commitment	363	45%	419	52%	10	1%	7	1%	3.4	Accepted	
19	Giving accelerated approval to members of staff who intend to embark on career development programme encourages job commitment	573	72%	187	23%	28	4%	11	1%	3.6	Accepted	
20	Workers who experience harmonious working relationship with their superior officers exhibits high level of job commitment	530	66%	219	27%	46	6%	4	1%	3.6	Accepted	
21	Non-involvement of members of staff in decision-making processes does not affect job commitment	31	4%	22	3%	426	53%	320	40%	1.7	Accepted	
Average Total		359	45%	246	30%	116	15%	77	10%			
Grand Mean											3.1	

Table 25 showed mean scores ranging from 1.7 to 3.6 of items 17-21 on influence of managerial support on job commitment in public tertiary institutions. It also showed that 76% of total respondents were in support of the items while 24% were not in support. It equally showed a grand mean score of 3.1 which was above the decision level of 2.5 weighted mean. Therefore, question four was answered that managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the data presented and analysed were discussed in accordance with the findings of the study. The result in research question one indicated that the extent of social recognition for workers in public universities in Ondo State was low as presented in Table 1. This result is in congruence with Ahmad and Musbahu (2018) who reported that public tertiary institutions in Nigeria are facing the challenges of inadequate facilities to effectively carry out official duties, lack adequate provision for staff development, unfriendly welfare packages and remuneration. The result in research question two revealed that the extent of managerial support for workers in public universities in Ondo State was high as presented in Table 2. The result in research question three indicated that social recognition influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State as presented in Table 3. The results agreed with the findings of Ahmad, Abdul, Majid and Mohd-Zin (2015) that social recognition is a strong motivational tool that enriches workers' energies towards the accomplishment of organisational goals and objectives. Also, this finding is in congruence with Ahmad, Bilal and Bibi (2020) who reported that recognition has significant positive relationship with personnel commitment to work. The result in research question four revealed that managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State as presented in Table 4. The result agreed with findings of Danesi (2011) who submitted that workers who receive more support from their superiors show more commitment to their organisation than those who receives less support.

Findings

The findings of the study that:

1. extent of social recognition for workers in public universities in Ondo State was low.
2. extent of managerial support for workers in public universities in Ondo State was high.
3. social recognition and managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State.
4. managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it was concluded that extent of social recognition for workers in public universities in Ondo State was low. Also, the study helped to conclude that extent of managerial support for workers in public universities in Ondo State was high. In addition, social recognition and managerial support influence workers' affective job commitment in public universities in Ondo State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government and school management should collaborate to organise annual awards of recognition for teaching and non-teaching staff in public universities.
2. School management and Head of Departments should endeavour to involve members of staff in decision making processes to get inputs before final decisions. Also, prompt approval should be given to workers who intend to embark on career development programme.

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